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SUSHEAT is a pioneering European project aimed at integrating waste heat and renewable energy for sustainable heat upgrade in industry.

The SUSHEAT project aims to develop innovative technologies tailored for flexible and efficient industrial heat generation at high temperatures ranging from 150°C to 250°C. These solutions will be validated in cutting-edge laboratories. A European consortium is working to reshape industrial heat generation through an advanced **Stirling-cycle High-Temperature Heat Pump (HTHP)** and novel technologies, such as a bio-inspired phase change material (PCM) **Thermal Energy Storage (TES)** system, and a **Control and Integration Twin (CIT)** system that utilizes advanced decision-making algorithms.

KTH Presents SUSHEAT Research on Industrial Decarbonization at Major Energy Conferences

At two recent conferences, **SolarPACES 2024** and **Enerstock 2024**, KTH presented distinct aspects of their research, each targeting innovative solutions to decarbonize industrial heat generation. [Read more](#)

SUSHEAT at Technology Talks 2024: Energy-Intensive Sectors Key to Europe's TripleTransition

SUSHEAT project partner RTDS Group participated in Technology Talks 2024, highlighting the critical role of industrial decarbonization in meeting Europe's climate goals and advancing the green transition. [Read more](#)

Interview with Thomas Nowak

Join us for an insightful interview with **Thomas Nowak**, Vice President of Quantum and former Secretary General of the European Heat Pump Association (EHPA), recorded at **TechTalks 2024 Austria** on September 12 in Vienna. In this video, Thomas shares his expertise on the vital role of heat pumps as a clean technology for industrial decarbonization in Europe.

[Watch full interview](#)

Recap of the SUSHEAT General Assembly: Strengthening Partnerships and Progress

Twelve months into the project, the consortium presented significant milestones achieved during its 2nd Consortium Meeting in Lleida, Spain. The University of Lleida team highlighted advancements in designing a novel Thermal Energy Storage (TES) unit using phase change material (PCM), while KTH Royal Institute of Technology presented the Laboratory Test Rig design that will simulate waste heat for testing purposes. A 3D model of the thermal energy storage unit was showcased to demonstrate the novel heat exchange system design.

[Read more](#)

Cluster Webinar: Industrial Heat Pumps to Pave Europe's Path to Net Zero

In Europe's decarbonisation journey, heat pump technologies are essential for sustainable heating and cooling, representing about 60% of energy consumption in the industrial sector. The recent webinar, "[Sustaining Success of Industrial Heat Pumps – A Call to Action!](#)", hosted by the European Heat Pump Association, showcased success stories that promote high-temperature industrial heat pumps.

This event was part of three EU-funded initiatives—[SUSHEAT](#), [PUSH2HEAT](#), and [SPIRIT](#)—aimed at advancing the adoption of high-temperature heat pumps (HTHP) in the industry.

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SUSHEAT COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

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